

Original Article

ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCY NEEDS OF BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITIES FOR SUCCESSFUL SMALL-SCALE BUSINESS IN ENUGU STATE*Okon Nnaemeka*

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DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17912023>

Abstract

This study focused on Entrepreneurial Competency Needs of Business Education Students' in Universities for Successful Small-Scale Businesses in Enugu State. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The population for the study was 91 business educators and university graduate entrepreneurs. The entire population was used in the study because the population was small and manageable. A 61-item structured questionnaire was developed and used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from Department of Technology and Vocational Education and one from Science and Computer Education (Measurement and Evaluation Unit), all in Faculty of Education Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability Coefficient of the three sections of the instrument and they ranged from .66 to .77 while the reliability Coefficient of the whole instrument gave a value of .69. The data collected were analyzed using mean with standard deviation while t-test statistic was used to test the null hypothesis at .05 level of significance at appropriate degree of freedom. The result of the findings revealed that all the items under managerial competency, interpersonal competency and, accounting competency were highly needed by Business Education students in universities for successful small-scale businesses in Enugu State. The null hypotheses tested showed no significant difference in the mean ratings of Business Educators and graduate entrepreneurs to the research question. Based on these findings, some implications were deduced and it was recommended among others that, universities offering business education program should ensure that entrepreneurial competencies are incorporated in their program to prepare the students adequately for small scale businesses. Managerial competencies in small scale business should be taught to the students to prepare them for effective management of their business activities. The identified interpersonal competencies should be part of the students' training to enable them to relate well with the public. Business educators should ensure that accounting competencies for financial management of small-scale businesses are taught to the students to enable them have skills in processing accounts, receivable and account payable to small scale business.

Keywords: *Entrepreneurial Competencies, Business Education Students, Small-Scale Businesses, Managerial and Interpersonal Skills, Enugu State Universities.*

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship development and small-scale business have received increasing attention in recent research due to their contributions to a country's economy and to human development. The place of entrepreneurship in today's business world is vital: students, after appropriate university training, may either become employed or become self-reliant. Therefore, to become self-reliant and profit from small-scale business requires the acquisition of skills, ideas and managerial competencies for effective organization, decision-making and actualization of set goals. For example, entrepreneurship has been conceptualized as a process of exploring business opportunities in the marketplace and arranging the resources required for exploiting them for long-term gain. (Asenge, 2018). Similarly, other scholars viewed entrepreneurship as the willingness and ability of an individual to seek out investment opportunities, establish, control and direct production processes of goods and services successfully and bear the attendant risks. (Mohammed, Ibrahim & Shah, 2017). Entrepreneurship can also be regarded as the effort to create purposeful change in a firm's economic and social potential. (Okoye, 2018). Further, entrepreneurship is any attempt at a venture creation such as a new business start-up, expansion of an existing business by an individual or team or a corporate body. (Adamu Babayayi, Zubairu & Musa Badara, 2022). Other researchers assert that entrepreneurship involves more than just business start-up; it also includes acquiring educational training to make gains in the business world, given that small-scale business is long recognized as instruments of economic growth and development. (Ogbari 2018). Some scholars note that entrepreneurial actions are the ultimate drivers of business cycles and economic development, whether in large, medium or small-scale businesses. (Gautam & Singh, 2015)

Small-scale enterprises serve the grassroots by creating jobs and incomes for low-level people, thus contributing to both human and economic development. (Apaokueze, 2021).

An entrepreneur is a person who takes business risks, assumes financial responsibilities, dictates the pace of the business, earns the interest and bears loss alone including his personal assets. (Falobi, Ishola & Jacob, 2019). Entrepreneurs also possess characteristics which give them the fortitude to continue despite obstacles and the ability to cope effectively in virtually all situations. (Mohammed, Ibrahim & Shah, 2017). They see opportunities, commercialize them, and in the process create wealth and jobs that benefit the rest of society. (Asenge, 2018). An entrepreneur finances and manages his/her business based on relevant training acquired. For instance, students of business education acquire such training through a business education program offered in universities.

Business education has been explained and defined by various authors. Business education plays an important role in the development of entrepreneurial mindsets and talents, especially in enhancing entrepreneurial competencies. (Ogundele, 2018). Business education is widely given high priority on the agenda of many governments, which depend on the development of entrepreneurship through business education as a major source for economic prosperity, growth, development and self-reliance among graduates. (Okoye, 2018). Business education is a concept which entails not only quality education but also practical, theoretical and competency development that help an individual function effectively in society. (Falobi, Ishola & Jacob, 2019). Business education is delivered in higher education, especially in universities. It consists of:

- Office education (a vocational education programme for office careers)
- General business education (a programme meant to provide students with information and

competencies needed in managing personal business affairs).

In this vein, graduates who have passed through a business education programme in universities need to be equipped with the necessary competencies to enhance their functionality after graduation. Competency was described as the state of being functionally adequate or having knowledge, skill, attitude and good judgment required to perform successfully at a specified proficiency level in a given work. (Adamu Babayayi, Zubairu & Musa Badara, 2022). In the context of this study, competency is the ability of a graduate from a business education programme in the university, to start up a business and do well in it based on the necessary skills acquired. (Falobi, Ishola & Jacob, 2019). Entrepreneurial competency is the ability of business education students to acquire the required skills, knowledge and attitude in order to perceive business opportunities. (Mohammed, Ibrahim & Shah, 2017). Entrepreneurial competencies are skills necessary for an entrepreneur to venture into an enterprise and run it successfully. (Asenge, 2018). The acquisition of employable skills through business education will reduce unemployment and, in turn, encourage self-reliance among business education graduates who embark on small-scale business.

Small-scale businesses are viewed as businesses that are independently owned and managed, in their dominant field of operation by private individuals, and intended to meet income and employment needs. (Okoye, 2018). Small-scale businesses usually have the following characteristics: the manager is the owner; capital is supplied by the owner; ownership is held by an individual or small group; operations are mainly local; and the relative size of the firm within its industry is small. (Falobi, Ishola & Jacob, 2019). Small-scale business is described as a seedbed for innovative ideas, growth and self-reliance among graduates. (Asenge, 2018). Small-scale businesses

also play a strategic role in economic development and provision of employment for a reasonable percentage of the population. (Apaokueze, 2021).

Worldwide, it has been identified that the most pragmatic solution to unemployment is through encouraging and promoting small-scale businesses. The establishment of small-scale enterprises plays vital roles: they not only produce for local consumption, but for export in international markets, thereby earning scarce foreign exchange. (Adewumi & Cele, 2023). Among industrialized nations, small-scale enterprises play pivotal roles in reducing unemployment, poverty and at the same time in the development of the economy and individuals. (Gautam & Singh, 2015) Given the role of small-scale business, there is need for entrepreneurial competency of business education students to be developed for success in this critical sector of the economy. This can be achieved through skills acquisition at the university level.

The objectives of every education system are geared towards equipping individuals who enroll into universities with the necessary skills to function effectively in society after graduation. A university is a tertiary institution that provides the training that prepares functional individuals that can work in various sectors of the economy and contribute significantly to the economic development of the nation. (Okoye, 2018). Business education students in universities need entrepreneurial competencies that will equip them with relevant skills for successful small-scale business on graduation. For example, business education students require marketing and financial competencies for successful management of small and medium-scale business. (Adewumi & Cele, 2023).

Management is the process of getting things done through people in an effective and efficient manner. (Adamu Babayayi, Zubairu & Musa Badara, 2022). Management is also viewed as the coordination of all the resources of an organization through the

processes of planning, organizing, directing and controlling in order to attain organizational goals. (Mohammed, Ibrahim & Shah, 2017). Desirable qualities that every person who aspires to be self-employed must possess are essential, especially given technological growth and development. It is only when these qualities and competencies are in place that business education students will be self-reliant on graduation. Business education students therefore need to possess business managerial, interpersonal, accounting and marketing competencies among others to achieve their goals in the world of small-scale development upon graduation.

Interpersonal skills are those skills needed to communicate effectively with a person or group of people including communication, decisiveness, self-confidence, work attitude and assertiveness. (Falobi, Ishola & Jacob, 2019). Accounting skills are important for successful entrepreneurial development. (Mohammed, Ibrahim & Shah, 2017). Accounting and financial skills help a business education graduate ascertain the financial position of a business, including knowledge of accounting and costing, ability to interpret financial statements, understanding payroll and various documents. (Adewumi & Cele, 2023). Therefore, there is an urgent need for business education students to be equipped with the necessary competencies for self-reliance and development of small-scale business as potential entrepreneurs, especially in Enugu State.

Enugu State is an inland state in south-eastern Nigeria, whose capital is Enugu (meaning “top of the hill”). The state shares boundaries with Anambra State, Abia State, Kogi State on the north, while Benue and Ebonyi are on the east. Enugu and Nsukka are its major towns. Enugu was the headquarters of the former East Central State and Eastern Nigeria. The state is one of the thirty-six states constituting the Nigerian federation. It was created on 27 August 1991 alongside other states by

former President Ibrahim Babangida. The state has a total of 17 local government areas. Nigeria’s first indigenous university, the University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN) is located in the state. The state also hosts the Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), the Institute of Management and Technology (IMT), Federal Cooperative College Oji River (FCCO), the Enugu State College of Education (Technical), and many other private tertiary institutions.

The educational institutions and the geographical location of Enugu State provide a great advantage for business education graduate entrepreneurs to perform well in small and medium enterprises by becoming self-reliant. The establishment of small-scale enterprises plays vital roles in society: the enterprises not only produce for local consumption, but for export in international markets, thereby earning foreign exchange. (Adewumi & Cele, 2023). Among the industrialized and developing nations alike, small-scale enterprise plays pivotal roles in eradicating unemployment and poverty while at the same time developing the economy and individuals. (Gautam & Singh, 2015) However, many businesses are not successful because graduate entrepreneurs are not competent to run them; this may result from not acquiring the required training that will make them competent. (Falobi, Ishola & Jacob, 2019). Hence, there is the need to determine the entrepreneurial competencies required by business education students for success in small-scale business upon graduation.

Statement of the Problem

The importance of entrepreneurship and small-scale business within the contemporary economic development is vital. Considering the role entrepreneurship has played in the development of hands and minds of the university graduates, its critical roles to the economies of nations are now widely acknowledged. It is therefore very important that students of business education equip themselves

with entrepreneurial competencies to enable them function effectively, own and manage their small-scale businesses.

The researcher observed that many small-scale businesses do not see the light of the day probably because students of business education lack some vital competencies that would enable them succeed on graduation. Let us take a walk around some small scale business that has boomed and are nowhere to be found or have lost their strength. Eg.UAC, UTC, AG Leventis, Chris Chemist, Chicken republic among others. Today, not many of these organizations can compete favorably with international counterparts, may be as a result of business education students do not possess entrepreneurial competencies needed for successful small scale business. It is speculated that the failure of these companies was as a result of lack of needed competencies by the business owners or their employees or could be that their competencies are still inadequate among university business education students.

All these observations show the need for an alternative opportunity to improve the living standard of business education students on graduation. The success of business education students on graduation may largely be dependent on effective of these competencies. It is against this background that it becomes pertinent to explore the Entrepreneurial competency needs of business education students in universities for successful small-scale business in Enugu state.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to determine, the entrepreneurial competency needs of business education students in universities for successful small-scale business in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to determine;

1. Managerial competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State.

2. Interpersonal competency needs of business education student for successful small-scale business in Enugu State.

3. Accounting competency needs of business education student for successful small-scale business in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research question guided the study

1. What are the managerial competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State?

2. What are the interpersonal competency needs of business education student for successful small-scale business in Enugu State?

3. What are the accounting competency needs of business education student for successful small-scale business in Enugu state?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of the Business Educators and small-scale business graduate entrepreneurs on business managerial competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of the Business Educators and small-scale business graduate entrepreneurs on the interpersonal competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of Business Educators and small-scale business graduate entrepreneurs on the accounting competency needs of business education students, for successful small-scale business in Enugu State

Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. According to Nworgu (2015), descriptive survey research design is one which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from a few people or items regarded as being representative of the entire group. The research was conducted in Enugu State, Nigeria, selected for its strong educational and commercial environment.

The population consisted of 91 respondents. 30 business educators from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, and Enugu State University of Science and Technology, and 61 university graduate entrepreneurs across the 17 Local Government Areas of Enugu State. Because the population size was manageable, the entire population was studied, and no sampling was done.

Data were collected using a 47-item structured questionnaire developed by the researcher, divided into two parts: Part I (personal data) and Part II (Three sections covering managerial, interpersonal and accounting).

The instrument was validated by three experts two in Business Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation unit of Department of Mathematics and Computer Education from Enugu State University of Science and Technology, who reviewed it for clarity

and relevance. The reliability was tested using the Cronbach Alpha method on 20 respondents in Anambra State, yielding coefficients ranging from 0.66 to 0.77 and an overall reliability index of 0.69, confirming internal consistency.

A total of 91 questionnaires were distributed with the help of three trained assistants, and 85 properly completed copies were retrieved, giving a 93.41% return rate. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and t-test statistics to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

The decision was based on the principle of lower and upper limit of the mean, thus;

Very high Needed (VHN)	3.50-4.00
Highly Needed (HN)	2.50-3.49
Slightly Needed (SN)	1.50 – 2.49
Not Needed (NN)	1.00 – 1.49

The null hypotheses will be rejected if the t-calculated value is greater than the critical or t-table value, but when the t-calculated value is less than the critical table the null hypotheses will not be rejected.

RESULT

Research Question 1

What are the managerial competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State?

Table 1:

Mean ratings with standard deviation of business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the managerial competency needs of business education students for small scale business in Enugu state.

S/N	Managerial competency needs include	Business educators n = 22		Small scale entrepreneurs n = 63		Overall		Decision
		□	SD	□	SD	□	SD	
1	Planning skill	3.55	0.51	3.59	0.59	3.58	0.56	VHN
2	Analytical reasoning of issues	3.36	0.66	3.68	0.47	3.60	0.54	VHN
3	Organizing skills	3.45	0.67	3.51	0.59	3.49	0.61	HN
4	Controlling skills	3.27	0.63	3.48	0.50	3.42	0.50	HN
5	Coordinating skill	3.14	0.77	3.59	0.56	3.47	0.65	HN
6	Manage time and meet job schedules	3.23	0.75	3.44	0.53	3.39	0.60	HN

7	Evaluate all activities based on set goals	3.45	0.60	3.35	0.57	3.38	0.58	HN
8	Organize resources for goal attainment	3.41	0.50	3.48	0.56	3.46	0.55	HN
9	Make long and short term plan	3.55	0.59	3.49	0.67	3.51	0.65	VHN
10	Generate ideas suitable to the Opportunities identified	3.45	0.67	3.52	0.59	3.51	0.61	VHN
11	Identify business opportunities	3.55	0.51	3.40	0.64	3.44	0.61	HN
12	Make appropriate use of feed back	3.59	0.50	3.56	0.59	3.56	0.57	VHN
Grand mean and SD		3.42	0.61	3.51	0.57	3.48	0.59	HN

Note: \bar{x} = Mean, SD, Standard deviation, VHN = Very highly Needed, HN Highly Needed.

The result presented in Table 1 above shows that the overall mean rating for items 1, 2, 9, 10 and 12 are 3, 5, 8, 3.360, 3.51, 3.51 and 3.56 respectively indicating very highly needed. This means that the items are very highly needed by the business education students in the successful management of small-scale businesses. The remaining items have mean rating ranging from 3.49 to 3.38 indicating highly needed. The implication of this result is that the items are highly needed as managerial competency of business education students in Small Scale Management. The low grand mean of 3.48

further shows that the itemized are highly needed managerial competency of business education students for successful small-scale businesses in Enugu State. The low standard deviation of 0.59 indicates that the respondents have similar view to the items.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of the business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the managerial competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State

Table 2:

t-test result of the mean rating of business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the managerial competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State.

Status	\bar{x}	SD	N	df	P	t-cal	t-tab	Decision
Business educators	3.42	0.61	22	83	0.05	0.4687	1.99	Not Significant
Small scale graduate entrepreneurs	3.51	0.57	63					

Note: \bar{x} = Mean, SD, Standard deviation, N = Number, Df = degree of freedom, t-cal= t calculated, t-tab = t-table value

Table 2 above shows that the calculated t-value of 0.4687 is less than the critical table value of 1.99 at 0.05 level of significant. Since the t-table value is more than t-calculated, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant. The implication is that there is no significant difference between the mean

rating of business educators and the small scale graduate entrepreneurs on the managerial competency needs of business education students for successful small scale business in Enugu state.

Research Question 2

What are the interpersonal competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State?

Table 3:
Mean rating with standard deviation of business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the interpersonal competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state

S/N	Managerial competency needs include	Business educators n = 22		Small scale entrepreneurs n = 63		Overall		Decision
		□	SD	□	SD	□	SD	
13	Communicate verbally	3.09	0.79	3.37	0.49	3.29	0.59	HN
14	Negotiate with others	3.36	0.58	3.27	0.68	3.29	0.65	HN
15	Act positively and decisively with available facts	3.18	0.73	3.24	0.56	3.22	0.61	HN
16	Solve problems in a system	3.45	0.67	3.38	0.66	3.40	0.66	HN
17	Take a decision	3.14	0.99	3.33	0.65	3.28	0.75	HN
18	Be assertive	3.18	0.80	3.40	0.64	3.34	0.68	HN
19	Work under pressure	3.32	0.72	3.48	0.50	3.44	0.57	HN
20	Manage time effectively	3.27	0.63	3.49	0.67	3.44	0.66	HN
21	Develop good listening skill	3.45	0.99	3.35	0.57	3.31	0.69	HN
22	Be self confidence	3.27	0.63	3.60	0.49	3.52	0.55	VHN
23	Have a team work spirit	2.59	0.50	3.53	0.50	3.36	0.69	HN
24	Have a positive work attitude	3.23	0.75	3.48	0.50	3.41	0.74	HN
25	Have a flexible working arrangement	3.45	0.67	3.37	0.62	3.39	0.64	HN
26	Deal with failure	3.27	0.70	3.19	0.67	3.21	0.67	HN
27	Deal with issues	3.32	0.72	3.24	0.64	3.26	0.66	HN
28	Manage anger constructively	3.36	0.85	3.38	0.66	3.34	0.70	HN
Grand mean and SD		3.25	0.73	3.38	0.59	3.34	0.66	HN

Note: □ = Mean, SD, Standard deviation, VHN = Very highly Needed, HN Highly Needed.

The result of data analysis presented in table 3 shows the mean responses with the corresponding standard deviation of business educators and the small-scale business entrepreneurs on the interpersonal competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business. The mean rating for item 22 is 3.52 indicating very highly needed interpersonal competency for successful small-scale

business. The remaining 15 items have mean rating ranging from 3.21 to 3.44 showing highly needed. This implies that the items are the interpersonal competency needs by business education students for successful small-scale business. The overall grand mean rating of 3.34 shows that the items are highly needed for successful small-scale business by business education students. The low standard deviation value of 0.66 indicates that the respondents have homogenous opinion in their responses.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of the business educators and small-scale business

graduates' entrepreneurs on the interpersonal competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state.

Table 4: t-test result of the mean rating of business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the interpersonal competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state.

Status	\bar{x}	SD	N	df	P	t-cal	t-tab	Decision
Business educators	3.25	0.73	22	83	0.05	0.649	1.99	Not Significant
Small scale graduate entrepreneurs	3.38	0.59	63					

Note: \bar{x} = Mean, SD, Standard deviation, N = Number, Df = degree of freedom, t-cal= t calculated, t-tab = t-table value

The summary of t-test analysis presented in table above shows that the t-calculated value of 0.649 is less than the t-table value of 1.99 at 0.05 level of significant and 83 degree of freedom. Since the t-critical is more than the t-table value the null hypothesis not significant this implies that status of

the respondents have no significant influence on their responses to the 16 items as the interpersonal competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state

Research question 3

What are the accounting competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state?

Table 5:

Mean rating with standard deviation of business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the accounting competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state

S/N	Managerial competency needs include	Business educators n = 22		Small scale entrepreneurs n = 63		Overall		Decision
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
29	Reconcile bank statement	3.77	0.43	3.59	0.59	3.64	0.55	VHN
30	Have knowledge of Accounting Information Systems	3.32	0.84	3.41	0.73	3.39	0.76	HN
31	Make use of Accounting Software	3.41	0.80	3.43	0.67	3.42	0.69	HN
32	Draw up a profit and loss account	3.36	0.66	3.40	0.61	3.39	0.62	HN
33	Have an analytical reporting	3.09	0.75	3.49	0.67	3.39	0.71	HN
34	Manage Assets effectively	3.09	0.68	3.27	0.54	3.22	0.59	HN
35	Prepare staff payroll	3.41	0.68	3.41	0.61	3.42	0.63	HN

36	Have proper Bookkeeping	3.36	0.66	3.13	0.79	3.1	0.76	HN
37	Identify business opportunities	3.05	0.65	3.21	0.70	3.1	0.69	HN
38	Keep debtors and creditors ledger	3.45	0.86	3.43	0.67	3.4	0.71	HN
39	Work with spreadsheet	3.27	0.70	3.59	0.59	3.5	0.63	VHN
40	Prepare cost Accounting	3.45	0.51	3.27	0.54	3.3	0.54	HN
41	Manage debt and recovery	3.36	0.58	3.06	0.69	3.1	0.67	HN
42	Calculate all forms of Tax	3.45	0.67	3.32	0.47	3.3	0.53	HN
43	Have knowledge of Journal Entry preparation/posting	3.23	0.75	3.35	0.57	3.3	0.62	HN
44	Have knowledge of Ms Excel	3.41	0.80	3.38	0.68	3.3	0.71	HN
45	Prepare financial statements	3.09	0.75	3.49	0.67	3.3	0.71	HN
46	Interpret financial statement	3.18	0.73	3.35	0.57	3.3	0.62	HN
47	Interpret gross and net profit	3.27	0.74	3.32	0.47	3.3	0.56	HN
Grand mean and SD		3.32	0.70	3.36	0.62	3.3	0.65	HN

Note: □ = Mean, SD, Standard deviation, VHN = Very highly Needed, HN Highly Needed.

The result of data analysis presented in table 5 shows that accounting competency needs denoted by item 29 and 39 were identified by the respondents as very highly needed by business education student for successful small-scale business in Enugu state. Also, items 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46 and 47 with mean rating ranging from 3.14 to 3.44 were perceived by the respondents to be highly needed by business education students as accounting competency. The overall grand mean of 3.35 with standard deviation of 0.65 was obtained for all the items (29 to 47) thereby indicating that the

itemized accounting competency needs fall within the range of highly needed by business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State. The relatively low overall grand standard deviation of 0.65 indicates that the respondents did not differ remarkably in their opinion regarding the items as accounting competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the accounting competency needs

of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state

Table 6: t-test result of the mean rating of business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the accounting competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu State.

Status	\bar{x}	SD	N	df	P	t-cal	t-tab	Decision
Business educators	3.32	0.70	22	83	0.05	0.195	1.99	Not Significant
Small scale graduate entrepreneurs	3.36	0.62	63					

Note: \bar{x} = Mean, SD, Standard deviation, N = Number, Df = degree of freedom, t-cal= t calculated, t-tab = t-table value

Result of t-test analysis in Table 6 shows that the calculated t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 83 degree of freedom is 0.195 while the t-table value is 1.99. Since the critical value is more than the calculated t-value, the null hypothesis is therefore not significant for the 18 items. This invariably means that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of business educators and small-scale graduate entrepreneurs on the accounting competency needs of business education students for successful small-scale business in Enugu state.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that managerial competencies such as planning, analytical reasoning, organization, coordination, control, and time management are highly needed by business education students for successful small-scale business operations in Enugu State. Okoro and Okoro (2020) found that effective planning and decision-making enhance entrepreneurial sustainability. The result supports Akinola (2019), who maintained that sound managerial competence helps entrepreneurs utilize resources efficiently and achieve business goals.

Findings also showed that interpersonal competencies such as communication, negotiation, teamwork, decision-making, and anger management are highly needed. This aligns with Nwachukwu (2017), who noted that interpersonal skills strengthen entrepreneurs’ ability to network and build customer

relationships. Adebayo and Onifade (2021) also emphasized that communication and emotional intelligence are crucial for productive business relationships.

The study further showed that accounting competencies such as bank reconciliation, record-keeping, use of accounting software, payroll management, and tax computation are highly needed by business education students. This agrees with Ogwumike (2018), who found that accounting knowledge enhances decision-making and business sustainability. Similarly, Anene (2020) observed that poor financial management is a major cause of business failure among Nigerian entrepreneurs. The finding confirms Okpara and Idoko (2019) that accounting literacy enables entrepreneurs to monitor performance and manage resources effectively.

Across all the competency areas managerial, interpersonal and accounting, the study found no significant difference between the views of business educators and graduate entrepreneurs. This aligns with Okwu and Igwe (2018), who found that both groups recognize similar skill sets as vital for entrepreneurial success. The shared perception indicates a close link between business education training and real-world entrepreneurial practice.

Conclusion

The study concluded that business education students in universities across Enugu State lack adequate entrepreneurial competencies needed for successful participation in small-scale business ventures. This finding calls for a reorientation of

business education towards practical, skill-based training that equips students for self-employment and enterprise development.

The results revealed that managerial competencies are crucial for effective planning, coordination, and control of business resources. Business education programs should therefore emphasize managerial skill development to help students navigate the realities of business operations.

Findings on interpersonal competencies indicate that communication, teamwork, and relationship management are vital for business sustainability. Business educators should integrate interactive and experiential learning methods that promote these interpersonal skills.

In addition, the study established the importance of accounting competencies in ensuring proper financial management and accountability. Business education should provide students with hands-on experience in bookkeeping, budgeting, and financial control to support sound decision-making.

In summary, developing these core entrepreneurial competencies managerial, interpersonal, and accounting is essential for preparing business education students to create and manage successful small-scale enterprises, thereby contributing to

employment generation and economic growth in Enugu State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Curriculum Enrichment: Universities and curriculum planners in business education departments should ensure that entrepreneurial competencies are fully incorporated into the Business Education curriculum. This will adequately prepare students for self-employment and successful participation in small-scale business ventures.

2. Managerial Skill Development: Business educators and faculty heads should emphasize the teaching and practical application of managerial competencies. They should design workshops, simulations, and case studies that help students develop the ability to plan, organize, and control business operations effectively.

3. Interpersonal Competency Training: Business education lecturers and program coordinators should integrate interpersonal skill development such as communication, teamwork, and relationship management into classroom activities and field experiences. This will enhance students' capacity to relate effectively with clients, employees, and partners in real business environments.

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